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DocEnhance

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A good practice recommendation for DocEnhance course concept implementation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Given the ongoing changes of doctoral education in Europe and globally, new, more networked, and collaborative resources are in great demand. The DocEnhance deliverable 3.5 *A good practice recommendation for DocEnhance course concept implementation* provides detail insight into how the three transferable skills courses: 1. Data stewardship 2. Supervision, and 3. Career management & entrepreneurship available on the DocEnhance courses website: <https://courses.docenhance.eu/>, can be implemented into practice and further tailored to cater for different audiences and participants in various national, local contexts. Deliverable 3.5 and the online course materials themselves, provide both motivation for local use and adaptation of the three courses developed and piloted during the project. It provides any prospective local teacher across European HEIs details on running the course, on scalability, possibilities for different course format executions, credit allocation, and uses of the course materials as a resource for self-study.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The course resources developed in the DocEnhance project mirror the broader ongoing changes of doctoral education in Europe. There is an increasing demand for new, more networked, online resources for researchers at PhD, post-doctoral and more senior levels across disciplines. The university will be increasingly hybrid (EUA 2021), allowing for both digital and physical learning and resources. Digital resources and infrastructures are clearly among the key trends transforming the face of doctoral education (EUA-CDE 2022). Digital courses made available across universities provide teachers with resources that can be further modified for online and f2f teaching. At the same time, they also provide learners the opportunity to build their knowledge and skills either through training, or at their own pace, focusing on their goals and needs to fill personal skills gaps.

The three courses developed in DocEnhance: 1. Data stewardship 2. Supervision and 3. Career management & Entrepreneurship represent key skills areas central to all doctoral candidates and their supervisors. The skills areas of the courses are also crucial when preparing modern doctors for a career both in and outside the academia (SuperProfDoc 2017). The courses were developed jointly, considering differences in target groups, means of flexible course execution and the need for self-study materials independent of time and place. Proof-of-concept was secured by piloting the courses in two rounds in a total of 7 DocEnhance universities. The iterative process during the project consisted of skills identification and prioritization, development of course content, implementation, and finally the evaluation of pilot courses. The integration of resources on the DocEnhance Platform followed this process with two loops (see Figure 1. below), to ensure that the main DocEnhance outputs are relevant and ready to use when the project ends. Each of the loops was followed by stakeholder workshops to evaluate and validate the interim prototypes of the DocEnhance Platform and its content.

The development, piloting and implementation of the courses during the project has been outlined in deliverables 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. The focus here is therefore on how to best implement the finished resources, at the completion of the project, and how local experts and teachers can make use of them across European HEIs to best suit the local, national needs, target groups, and outcomes. All course materials will be made available in the Moodle learning management system (LMS), available at <http://docenhance.eu>.

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Figure 1.

Given that the course structures vary somewhat according to topic area and target group, the implementation guides of each course are presented below in turn.

2. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE FOR THE COURSE DATA STEWARDSHIP

The DocEnhance Data Stewardship Course is a course primarily made for PhD candidates, offering a basic understanding of how to manage their data in their PhD project in accordance with best practice and the FAIR) principles <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>. The course should preferably be undertaken at an early stage of a candidate's PhD project. That way, the candidates can benefit from the knowledge acquired from the course contents, as they proceed with their PhD project. Putting their acquired knowledge to practical use will give the best learning outcome from this course.

The course consists of three modules:

Module 1

Module 1 introduces theory and best practice with video lectures and texts, organized in topical sessions, including lists of required and recommended readings. Each session also includes a quiz, where the candidates may test their acquired knowledge. In the end of Module 1 the candidates

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may do the multiple-choice exam. Passing the exam is a requirement for moving on to Module 2 and eventually Module 3.

The content of Module 1 is made available in the Moodle learning management system (LMS), available at <http://docenhance.eu>. Participants need to sign in, to get their personal exam certificate. Each participant will go through Module 1 individually without requiring teacher involvement. But there is a contact information for those who have questions to ask.

Preparations needed:

Module 1 may be done individually. But universities (or others) wanting to organise Module 2 and 3, to offer the full Data Stewardship course, may be advised to announce and promote the full course, including Module 1. Preparations for this would need to include decisions on the time schedule included in the announcement: candidates are recommended to start with Module 1, and the days when Module 2 and 3 will be run need to be specified. Instructions on how to sign up are also required. Universities planning to offer the course could do so in cooperation with other universities, allowing for participants from multiple institutions. To give participants ECTS credits or other type of credits from the course, administration must be undertaken locally. Questions regarding how to prepare and organise the course may be sent to help-desk at researchdata@hjelp.uit.no.

Module 2

In Module 2 the participants team up for sessions with assignments to be done as groupwork. Local hosting universities need to announce and organise a sign-up for Module 2, and book necessary facilities like rooms if the Module is run on site.

Module 2 consists of sessions covering all the core topics of research data management. Here the candidates may apply the knowledge acquired in Module 1 in their assignments. The groupwork needs to be organised and assisted by teachers and facilitators. The teachers are not meant to give regular lectures within the Data Stewardship topics, but rather, introduce the course participants to the assignments and secure that the participants understand the assignments and that the groupwork runs as it should. They also need to be available for answering questions.

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Module 2 also makes use of Moodle as LMS tool. However, only the teachers need to access the Module 2 content in Moodle. The teachers therefore need to pick and distribute assignments to the participating candidates they find suitable. This also includes pre-assignments that are meant to be done prior to the groupwork. The pre-assignments are meant as warm-up sessions for the candidates.

The Module consists of six sessions, each designed to take three hours to run. The sessions are flexible in the way that local organisers may choose to emphasise some sessions and reduce the workload on others. Organisers need to consider if an adjusted workload should affect the number of ECTS or other type of credits to be earned from the course.

Preparations needed:

- 1) Organising sign-up of candidates. Deciding the maximum capacity of attending candidates. Booking rooms in their local campus. Recruit teachers and assistants. It is recommended to have two or three teachers for a group of 20–30 participating candidates.
- 2) Deciding the time for Module 2 to be run, including how the sessions should be distributed over this time period. The module consists of six half day sessions, which may be run either concentrated over a period of three days or spread out over several days.
- 3) Preparing the group works. Go through the teacher guides for each assignment, including the exam assignment. Make sure all teachers have a common understanding of how the assignments should be understood. Make use of the contact address for assistance if needed. Distributing the pre-assignments and assignments at appropriate times before and during the Module 2 period. Preparing how to run the exam assignment.

Module 3

In Module 3 the candidates put their acquired data stewardship knowledge to practical use in cooperation with a business or public service office. The idea is to let the candidates put their skills in data management to use outside the academia.

Just as for Module 2, Moodle is used to hold information and tips for the teachers of Module 3. This includes a Community Resource Bank. Organisers of Module 3 are encouraged to contribute

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to the Resource Bank and thus help developing Module 3 into an even more useful resource in the time to come.

Module 3 will normally take three full days: Day one: Introduction of stakeholders and presentation of assignments. And if possible, get started on the assignments. Day two: Work on assignments. Day three: exam. Module 3 is very flexible. The workload and the types of assignments may be adopted and adjusted according to local needs and preferences. Organisers need to consider how any adjusted workload may affect the ECTS or other type of credits to be earned from the course.

3. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE FOR THE COURSE SUPERVISION

Doctoral education and doctoral candidates Across European HEIs and globally have a key role in new knowledge, and social, theoretical, and technical innovations production. Up-to-date, professional, high-quality PhD supervision is repeatedly identified as the crucial tool that supports impactful doctoral education and prepares doctoral candidates to contribute to research and society. PhD supervision training practice remains heterogeneous across European universities and globally. For this reason, the course on PhD supervision was designed as a malleable resource bank that can be tailored towards various local and national needs. The course resources can be used for online and face-to-face training courses, as self-training material, and as a resource used collectively to spark conversation on supervision on the faculty or doctoral programme level. The course materials and videos can also flexibly be tailored to focus on a specific theme around supervision like the beginning crucial phases of the supervisory relationship, conflict management, intercultural supervision etc. The course offers videos, teaching and reading resources, and formats for peer group-work that benefit and can be used when training both beginning and more mature supervisors, or to include industry supervisors. Expert teachers or facilitators are invited to add further elements, exercises, and resources to better cater for local needs. Credit allocation needs to be calculated case-by-case and a certificate template is provided for potential local use.

The basic idea behind the PhD Supervision course resource development was, out of necessity, malleability. Any prospective teacher should approach it as a resource bank to choose elements from and adding local ones to suit the target group in question. The focus of the course materials is less on pedagogical aspect of supervision, and more on the institutional, changing institutional framing of supervisors' crucial role, and the widening scope of transferable skills supervisors should see as part of doctoral research training.

The course outcomes and learning targets can include i.e. the following:

- providing crucial information on the institutional frames, resources, and key guidelines for supervisory practices in the local university, and internationally,
- discussing essential pedagogical, as well as the widening research skills that are part and parcel of supervision,
- helping participants integrate their own research mission into supervision practices
- breaking the solitude of supervision perceived as master-apprentice practice behind closed doors, and encouraging a more collegial, shared supervision & peer support culture,
- helping participants to identify key roles, tensions and dynamics, to reflect and further develop their own practices, and those in the supervisor community more broadly;
- providing tools and practical resources for participants to develop their own skills and well-being further as supervisors.

4. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE FOR THE COURSE CAREER MANAGEMENT & ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The DocEnhance “Career Management & Entrepreneurship” (CM&E) course is a primarily made for PhD candidates (although it can be easily extended to more senior researchers), to give them a basic understanding of the main competences and tools they need to develop and cultivate to manage their careers, and to develop an entrepreneurial venture. The course is built around the concept that entrepreneurial competences are key to face the challenges of a volatile and challenging job market, both outside and within academia.

The CM&E course has been developed during the entire duration of the DocEnhance project and piloted twice in two partner universities, UNL and TAU. The course material, targeted at trainers from other higher education institutions, is openly available with CC BY 4.0 license in the DocEnhance Moodle LMS.

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The course is structured in core modules that constitutes the basics for further developing the contents detailed as ancillary modules. The rationale for this approach is that, while entrepreneurship constitutes a potential career avenue, this is not the only option; on the other hand, entrepreneurial competences are also important to develop one's career in many work environments, including academia. We exploit this feature to intertwine the two contents together.

Given its modular nature, the course provides great flexibility for trainers to go in more depth into some parts, extend or omit others, and to tailor according to local needs and peculiarities. In fact, since some institutions might prefer to emphasize the aspects related to venture creation (or to career management), they have total freedom to do so. The most extreme case would consist in splitting the course into "entrepreneurial" and a "career management" stand-alone courses.

The material provided allows trainers to be inspired by the contents and build their course according to their expertise and experience. This feature will broaden the number of institutions that can make use of the course. On the other hand, the course provided is not a black box that any trainer can use. It requires expert trainers who know how to facilitate courses based on active learning and who are familiar with relevant parts of the contents.

5. LIFE COURSE OF THE COURSE MATERIALS PRODUCED AND RISK ANALYSIS

The courses developed in the DocEnhance project represent both core and more recent crucial skills and aspects of doctoral training. Whereas supervision has for long been considered at the core of any successful doctoral process, data management, entrepreneurship and detailed career planning are among newer training requirements. The current structure of the courses produced enables enriching each of the course resources and structures with additional content uploaded to the Moodle LMS by the trainers who teach and develop new materials or new modules.

The risk with any products developed within a finite project concern securing the life course and longer-term usability and relevance of such resources. The project logic that sustains and encourages international collaboration typically, out of necessity, finishes at the end of the project's financial incentive. To keep the DocEnhance platform alive, up to date, and of interest

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for higher education institutions across Europe, it would be worthwhile to plan for a long-term maintenance of the platform also after the end of the project.

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